

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.4

Technology Roadmap Development

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable involves the creation of a roadmap for further development of the X-Rotor concept. This document will focus on the process for creating the roadmap as well as the X-Rotor development next steps and future development plans. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete once the road map is made public and/or delivered to the executive management group.

1 Introduction

In the pursuit of advancing offshore wind energy solutions, the X-Rotor Offshore Wind Turbine Concept has emerged as a pioneering innovation with the potential to reshape the wind energy landscape. Within the framework of Work Package 8 (WP8) of the XROTOR project, a task has been undertaken to develop a roadmap for the further evolution of the X-Rotor concept. This technical report encapsulates the collaborative efforts of industry experts, stakeholders, and project partners aimed at charting a strategic course for the continued development and commercialization of the X-Rotor technology.

A key part of this roadmap is the establishment of the X-Rotor Panel of Experts or Industrial Advisory Board (IAB), a diverse panel spanning key stakeholders from the wind energy industry. From wind turbine OEMs and utilities to research organizations and investors, the IAB represents a comprehensive array of perspectives essential for informed decision-making and strategic guidance on X-Rotor next steps. Through a series of deliberations and engagements, the IAB has provided invaluable insights into the unique characteristics, challenges, and opportunities inherent to the X-Rotor Offshore Wind Turbine Concept.

Drawing upon the collective expertise of the X-Rotor IAB, this report looks at the unique selling points (USPs) of the X-Rotor concept, as well as the challenges it faces in its progression towards commercialization. From dissecting and analysing these factors, actionable recommendations have been formulated by the panel of experts to address existing challenges and capitalize on inherent strengths. Moreover, the report delineates a set of next-step recommendations aimed at pushing the concept forward on both technical and commercial fronts.

This roadmap combines technical knowledge, commercial acumen, and stakeholder collaboration. It serves as one potential route for advancing the X-Rotor Offshore Wind Turbine Concept.

2 Methodology

The following steps were completed for the creation of the X-Rotor roadmap for further development:

1. Formation of Expert Panel and IAB (Industrial Advisory Board): The initial phase of the X-Rotor roadmap creation involved assembling a distinguished panel of industry experts and members of the Industrial Advisory Board (IAB). This assembly aimed to encompass stakeholders from various sectors such as investors, developers, OEMs, operators, consultancies, and research bodies. Emphasis was placed on recruiting individuals holding senior or executive positions within the wind and finance industries to ensure a well-rounded and high-level perspective. After consultation with colleagues experienced in running IABs and steering committees and significant consideration by the authors, six members was

selected as the size of the IAB. Many more members could lead participants to “hide” in meetings and when input was required. Fewer than 6 members could mean a wide enough perspective was not gained. The consortium drew on their wide network to select the 6 members from investors, developers, OEMs, operators, consultancies, and research bodies

2. **Initial Group Meeting with Panel Members:** A key first step in the roadmap creation process was the commencement of an initial group meeting with the assembled panel members. This collective session served as an opportunity to introduce the X-Rotor Concept and delineate the overarching task of creating a roadmap for further development of the XROTOR. During this meeting, project objectives, scope, and expectations were outlined to provide clarity and alignment among all participants. Additionally, the session facilitated the solicitation of initial feedback to gauge panel members' understanding and interest in the X-Rotor concept, setting the stage for further engagements.
3. **Individual Consultations with Panellists:** Following the group meeting, individual consultations were conducted with each panel member to delve deeper into specific queries or concerns regarding the X-Rotor concept or the roadmap development task. These one-on-one meetings provided a conducive environment for personalized explanations and clarifications tailored to individual expertise and interests. By fostering open dialogue, these consultations aimed to encourage panel members to freely express their perspectives, insights, and recommendations, thereby enriching the collective understanding of the project and more importantly the concept.
4. **Distribution of Explainer Materials and Provocative Questions:** As part of the engagement process, materials explaining the unique characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses of the X-Rotor concept were distributed to each panellist. Accompanying these materials were thought-provoking questions designed to stimulate critical analysis and reflection for discussion in the panellist's own organisation and within their own network. The distribution emphasised the importance of thorough consideration and informed deliberation in shaping the roadmap development process, empowering panel members to engage deeply with the subject matter. It was felt if the panel members did not have a strong understanding of the unique characteristics of the concept, they would not be equipped to provide useful input to the future roadmap.
5. **Follow-up Meetings for Input Collection:** After the distribution of materials, follow-up meetings were scheduled with each expert to gather their input on strategies for advancing the X-Rotor concept beyond Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 3. These follow-up sessions provided an opportunity for panel members to offer concrete suggestions, innovative ideas, and practical recommendations based on their own domain knowledge and experience and that of their organisation and network. Through collaborative discussions, viable pathways for progression were identified, laying the groundwork for informed decision-making.

6. **Consensus Building and Determination of Next Steps:** The final phase of the roadmap creation process entailed consolidating input and feedback from all panellists to determine consensus on the subsequent steps for advancing the X-Rotor concept. Facilitated by iterative discussions and deliberations, the authors sought to identify common themes from the panel, areas of agreement, and divergent perspectives. By leveraging the collective expertise of the panel, consensus was reached on the next steps for advancing the X-Rotor concept beyond TRL 3. The outcomes of these deliberations were documented, culminating in the finalization of the development roadmap, complete with actionable recommendations.

Figure 1: Process for creation of further roadmap development

3 Outputs from Panel of Experts

Based on engagement with the XROTOR IAB, X-Rotor unique selling points (USP) and challenges were identified. This Section briefly notes the USPs and challenges, it makes recommendations for overcoming those challenges and concludes by recommending high level next steps that should be considered for the concept's further development.

XROTOR USP and Funding

Through IAB engagement, it was established that the X-Rotor concept has a number of potential benefits that should be highlighted as unique selling points for the concept. These benefits include:

- Lower LCoE than HAWTs
- Greater floating platform potential than HAWTS
- Higher density wind farm potential than HAWTS
- Stronger local content potential
- Reduced rare earth potential
- Reduced offshore working for maintenance
- Flexibility in turbine ratings based on market dynamics and regional suitability. Gradual progression in X-Rotor turbine ratings was recommended, starting with lower-rated turbines for market penetration and to avoid the current scaling issues being experienced by HAWT OEMs.

Along with the XROTOR benefits outlined above, the following points were also highlighted by the IAB for the next phase of X-Rotor development:

- Possible research funding sources include the US Department of Energy (DoE), Horizon Europe, EPSRC etc.
- Exploration of partnerships with industrial partners is recommended, with funding from legacy oil and gas companies more likely than traditional wind turbine OEMs.
- Challenges in attracting early adopters/investors are acknowledged, requiring identification and tailoring of unique selling points to specific funders and a willingness to share IP likely required.

XROTOR Barriers and Barrier Mitigation

Through IAB engagement, it has been established that the X-Rotor concept faces barriers to market entry primarily related to its novelty, lack of track record in the field, perceived risks and the dominance of major OEMs in the market. The IAB recommends that the following points should be considered for the next phase of the concept development to start addressing the barriers to market entry outlined above:

- Scaled prototyping is a vital step in de-risking new technology.
- At first onshore demos are recommended in countries supportive of innovative technologies with low permitting barriers.
- Focus on the United States and Middle East when looking for a site.
- Noise concerns and permitting issues will influence demo locations in the UK and Europe.
- The negative effect of a low efficiency scaled model is outweighed by the positive effect of physically proving the concept.
- If a whole scaled prototype is too costly, incremental proof-of-concept demonstrations should be considered. Focus on proving secondary turbine system viability and addressing technical uncertainties related to secondary rotors is recommended as they are one of the more novel parts of the turbine.

Recommended Next Steps from IAB

For the next project phase, it is recommended that the XROTOR team focus on the benefits/USPs of the X-Rotor outlined above. The specific benefit to highlight should be tailored depending on the funding source engaged. From the potential funders/investors mentioned above, most will focus on the potential for reduced LCoE as the primary driver for engagement, with the balancing of CAPEX and OPEX being secondary to overall cost-effectiveness. The IAB felt that the greatest commercial opportunity lies in floating platforms with a 3 bladed X-Rotor to be considered if it allows for lower LCoE from floating.

A scaled prototype or technology demo is recommended as soon as possible to help overcome the perceived risks of a novel concept and to validate existing computational models of the concept.

It is recommended that further work focuses on two areas, the first being computational development of the 3 bladed concept for floating wind energy and the second being hardware/prototype testing to de-risk and validate computational models of the 2 bladed concept.

Where possible, research funding should be obtained to avoid diluting IP. Potential sources are mentioned earlier in this document. When research funding is not available, or to leverage industrial expertise/experience, it is recommended that funding is sought from industrial partners, with legacy oil and gas companies thought the most likely to engage.

In conclusion, the XROTOR concept's success hinges on systematic addressing of barriers, strategic collaborations, and emphasis on unique and diverse X-Rotor advantages that appeal to a given funder, investor or partner.

4 Immediate and Longer-Term Next Steps for the X-Rotor

Immediate Next Steps (TRL4-6)

The immediate next steps for advancing the X-Rotor concept into Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4 to 6 involve hardware testing for the two bladed concept. Parallel to the hardware work, it should be the aim to conduct feasibility work on the three-bladed X-Rotor concept. Immediate next steps will involve undertaking design work necessary for the development of a scaled prototype that will take the project to and beyond TRL4. Following the design phase, a 10/1 scaled prototype will be engineered, with components manufactured in the UK. The selection of a 10/1 scaled prototype is based on the feasibility of transporting its largest parts in a standard 40-foot shipping container, enabling testing in low wind speed sites in Asia, such as Dubai or Malaysia. These low wind speed sites offer a dual advantage: they represent a potential niche market for the X-Rotor, while also providing a safer environment for testing compared to high wind speed sites. The scaled prototype may also contain a generator at the vertical axis for control and proof of concept purposes. The focus of the 10/1 scaled prototype will be on hardware proof of technical concept, rather than efficiency or cost potential. Funding for this phase will be sourced from research grants and/or from ex-oil and gas companies, as well as research grants.

TRL7-8 Development

Moving beyond TRL 6, the development of the X-Rotor concept will involve collaboration with existing wind energy companies or companies venturing into the renewable energy sector. This collaboration will aim to take the concept beyond TRL 6 and into the higher TRL levels 7 and 8. Additionally, funding avenues such as Horizon or other similar initiatives will be explored, allowing for the realization of full-scale prototypes. Existing Horizon opportunities such as the following would be ideal for XROTOR development beyond TRL 6: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl5-2024-d3-02-09>.

These opportunities enable the project to access resources and support necessary for advancing the X-Rotor concept towards commercialization and adoption.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the creation of the roadmap for further development of the X-Rotor concept has been a very useful step in defining the next steps for the concept. This deliverable, undertaken as part of Work Package 8, represents a collaborative industry wide effort aimed at determining a strategic course for the continued evolution and commercialization of the X-Rotor technology.

Through the establishment of the X-Rotor Panel of Experts and Industrial Advisory Board (IAB), comprising stakeholders from various sectors including investors, developers, OEMs, operators, consultancies, and research bodies, a diverse array of perspectives has been brought to this deliverable. That collective expertise has been key to identifying the unique selling points (USPs) and challenges facing the X-Rotor concept.

From the insights garnered through engagements with the IAB, actionable recommendations have been formulated to address existing challenges and capitalize on inherent strengths of the concept. These recommendations span both technical and commercial domains.

Looking ahead, the immediate next steps for advancing the X-Rotor concept into Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4 to 6 involve feasibility work on the three-bladed X-Rotor concept and the design of a scaled prototype. This prototype, engineered at a 10/1 scale and strategically designed to fit into a standard shipping container, will enable testing in low wind speed sites in Asia. Funding for this phase will be sourced from research grants and ex-oil and industrial partners.

Beyond TRL 6, the development trajectory of the X-Rotor concept will involve collaboration with existing wind energy companies and/or new entrants as well as exploration of funding avenues such as Horizon Europe, Innovate UK, Royal Academy of Engineering etc. These opportunities will facilitate the realisation of full-scale prototypes and provide the necessary resources and support for commercialization.

In summary, the success of the X-Rotor concept hinges on systematic addressing of technical and commercial barriers, strategic collaborations, and emphasis on its unique and diverse advantages. The next steps laid out in this deliverable are one of many potential routes to further development of the X-Rotor concept.